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ABSTRACTS

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Synthesis of biopolymer from food waste using genetically engineered bacteria

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Abstract: According to the United Nations, an estimated 17 per cent of total global food production is wasted annually. It jumps to a staggering 40% in India. In 2020, the Global Hunger Index (GHI) positioned India at 94 among 107 nations, and that implies just 13 nations performed more poorly than India when it came to meeting their populace's food needs. As many people still sleep without eating enough every day, food waste remains a serious cause for concern. Since, food waste when processed, either gets decomposed or is turned into biogas which only leads to the excess carbon emissions. Our main aim is to solve the enormous food waste issue while simultaneously minimizing the use of single-use plastics by replacing them with the more sustainable and durable option, bioplastics while incorporating AI. Food waste has been majorly linked to food processing and manufacturing. But on our end, we have observed it happening at the local messes, restaurants daily. Meanwhile, plastic trash is also a major source of contamination in the environment. Hence, by combining these two domains, we wish to execute our solution by exploring the capability of food waste being utilized as a bioplastic material. Subsequently, physical, thermal-compound, and biological approaches expected for preparation of bioplastic raw components from food waste will be accounted for. Alterations of various food waste components (e.g., cellulose, starch, chitin, and caprolactone) for PHA derived items were additionally thought of.

MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

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